

GENDER PARTICIPATION IN THE SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF RESOURCES WITHIN UPLAND AGROFORESTS IN LA UNION, PHILIPPINES

Lieslea M. Wagayen

*College of Agroforestry and Forestry, Don Mariano Marcos Memorial State University,
Bacnotan, La Union, Philippines*

PhD Program University of the Philippines, Los Banos, Laguna

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ABSTRACT

This study, conducted between February 25 and May 25, 2020, aimed to assess gender participation in sustainable resource management across three upland municipalities in La Union, Philippines. The research involved 145 respondents and employed descriptive statistics, including frequency counts, percentages, and means for data analysis. Findings revealed a predominant presence of male and married respondents, primarily leaseholders with extensive farming experience of nine years or more, cultivating an average area of 0.5 to 1.5 hectares. The majority reported a monthly income ranging from Php3,000 to Php5,000. Both male and female respondents exhibited moderate to very high levels of participation in project management, site preparation, maintenance, protection activities, and adoption of soil water conservation practices. Challenges encountered included irregular commitment of members and limited female participation in planning sessions, perceived as fairly serious by female respondents. However, male respondents did not rate these issues as significant. Overall, gender participation was not deemed critical across most project activities, suggesting potential areas for improvement.

Keywords: *Agroforestry, Gender participation, Soil and water conservation, Sustainable management, Upland*

INTRODUCTION

Situation Analysis

The Philippines is one of the world's largest archipelago nation situated in Southeast Asia in the Western Pacific Ocean. It is considered as one of the mega biodiversity countries in the world with a high percentage of flora and fauna endemism. Because of its archipelagic nature, Philippines is a culturally diverse country. With its topography consisting of mountainous terrains, dense forests, plains, and coastal areas, the Philippines is rich in biodiversity (United Nation Development Program, 2009).

Upland areas in the Philippines serve as the vital support system of the whole watershed continuum that activities in the areas may greatly influence the conditions in the lowland and coastal areas and a place where increasing population of the "poorest of the poor" lives and one which is expected to absorb more of the expanding population. The recent estimate of upland population in the Philippines is 17.8 M and 3.18 M households. However, if properly developed, it is a key to sustainable development and socio-economic progress. It can be a major government strategy to attain social stability (United Nation Development Program, 2009).

Uplanders also believe that they are the least addressed sector. Thus any form of assistance from the government or NGO's is a means of alleviating their socio-economic status. Majority of the 12 million populations of the Indigenous Peoples (IP's) reside in the upland which they claim as part of their traditional territories. Most of the remaining natural resources in the country are found within the traditional lands of Indigenous Peoples (IP's). The IP's represent nearly 14% of the country's population and considered poorest of the poor (Carig, 2012), the marginalized and the disadvantaged social group where illiterate, unemployed and where poverty is much higher than the rest of the population. In 2017, the percentage of families who rated themselves as poor was 50% in March, 44% in June, 47% in September and 44% in December, for an average quarterly rate of 46% for the whole year (Mangahas, 2018).

Rural development has been the goal of Philippine economic development for the reason that it has been the seat of age-long poverty and where the majority of the poor are still found in rural areas and in the agriculture sector, primarily as farmers and fishers. In 2012, extreme poverty in the Philippines was estimated at 19.2 percent of the population, or about 18.4 million people, based on the international poverty line of \$1.25 per day. Urban poverty, however, has been increasing in recent years. Migrants without jobs or with low-paying jobs are unable to afford decent housing. As a result, Philippine cities have high proportions of informal settlers who are among the "poorest of the poor" (Liacó, 2014).

Despite of having widespread poverty, the Philippines has fared relatively well in Human Development Index (HDI), particularly in comparison to other Southeast Asian nations. In 2012, Philippines' economy outpaced the growth of its neighboring countries with 6.6 percent growth rate (Rappler, 2013).

The goals of upland development include increased productivity, enhance sustainability through soil, water and mineral conservation, enhanced community participation and increased equitability along with the guidelines on how to achieve them (Cruz, et al, 2014).

Conservation of soil and water resources is important for sustainability of agriculture and environment. Soil and water resources are under immense pressure due to ever increasing population, thereby ensuring growing demand for food, fiber and shelter. Soil and water resources are being deteriorated due to different anthropogenic and natural factors. Soil erosion is one of the several major deteriorative processes which results in deterioration of the soil. It is the removal of soil due to movement of water and/or air and may lead to the significant loss of soil productivity, thus may lead to the desertification under sever conditions. Water and wind are the major factors which are responsible of soil erosion. Deforestation, over-grazing, mismanagement of cultivated soils, intensive cultivation and intensive urbanization are major factors triggering the soil erosion. For sustainable agriculture and environment, it is pertinent for the protection of soil resources against erosion. Different control measures should be adopted to protect the soil resources against erosion. The concept of soil conservation cannot be materialized without conserving and efficient use of water resources. It is therefore pre-requisite that soil conservation practices should be adopted. Soil conservation practice include soil management, crop management, engineering, range management and forestry operation (Bashir et al., 2017).

Soil and Water Conservation are those activities at the local level which maintain or enhance the productive capacity of the land including soil, water and vegetation in areas prone to degradation (Rafanan, 2018).

Philippine forest cover have degenerated beacuse of massive logging activities, extreme poverty and shifting cultivation. Current deforestation rate has been estimated at 100,000 ha per year. There are about 20 million Filipinos living in upland watershed areas, half of whom are dependent on shifting cultivation for livelihood. The continous influx of migrant communities has further aggravated the diminishing forest resources. Given the dependence of human and social life of products from the forest from wood to water and to the oxygen they produce, these consequences impinge on all sectors of the society (Mapili, 2019).

On the enhanced community participation and improved equitability, the following must be considered: system should fit local farming practices, farmer's capabilities, provide security to the land they till and to the trees, crops and livestock they raise, farmers or their organization should be provided with assistance and other forms of incentives like:

social infrastructure land tenure processing of contracts, M & E of different activities, preparation of resource management plan and resource management utilization, provision of farm inputs, product processing linkages assistance for the provision of other support services, the project should be gender-sensitive; and the system should be compatible with the customs, traditions and beliefs of the participants. Poverty and inequality have been recurrent challenges in the Philippines and have again come to the fore in the wake of the current global financial crisis and rising food, fuel, and commodity prices experienced in 2008.

In any program/project development endeavor, participation of project beneficiaries both men and women is vital in order to succeed. Participatory development stresses the importance of peoples' participation as a key element toward relevant and sustainable program. Participatory development is a peoples' oriented approach when it elicits a community's ability to solve their own problems. However, as to who are involved or participate in that development endeavor has become a crucial issue, such as gender issue (Oakley, 1988).

Development analysts have recognized now for several decades the need to ensure that gender is examined and integrated into development projects. In integrating gender into development, practitioners are responding to the priority needs of women and men, and being aware of what benefits or adverse effects could impact either. In taking account of gender, development practitioners and social movement activists are looking at disparities that exist in male and female rights, responsibilities, access to and control over resources, and voice at household, community and national levels. Men and women often have different priorities, constraints and preferences with respect to development and can contribute to, and be affected differently by, development projects and campaigning interventions. To enhance effectiveness, these considerations must be addressed in all program and campaign design and interventions. If such considerations are not addressed thoughtfully and adequately, these interventions can lead not only to inefficient and unsustainable results, but may also exacerbate existing inequities. Understanding gender issues can enable projects to take account of these and build in capacity to deal with inequitable impacts and to ensure sustainability (Parpart et al., 2000).

The history of this field dates back to the 1950s, when studies of economic development first brought women into its discourse (Moser, 1993), focusing on women only as subjects of welfare policies – notably those centered on food aid and family planning. The focus of women in development increased throughout the decade, and by 1962, the United Nations General Assembly called for the Commission on the Status of Women to collaborate with the Secretary General and a number of other UN sectors to develop a longstanding program dedicated to women's advancement in developing countries. A decade later in 1970s, feminist economist Ester Boserup pioneered and published a book entitled "Women's Role in Economic Development". This radically shifted perspectives of development and contributed to the birth of what eventually became the gender and development field (Robinson and Ross, 2007).

An early approach involved targeting women by project design and interventions which focused on women as a separate group. This was commonly referred to as WID (Women in Development). Critics of this approach pointed out that this did not address men, and a later model usually referred to as GAD (Gender and Development) concentrated more on project design and interventions that were focused on a development process that transforms gender relations. This aimed to enable women to participate on an equal basis with men in determining their common future. The Gender Equality approach is therefore about men and women and is thus a more comprehensive approach to analysis and design of development interventions because it takes into account the situation and needs of both men and women. It aims to involve both women and men in addressing their development problems, to reform institutions to establish equal rights and opportunities, and to foster economic development which strengthens equal participation. Such an approach aims to redress persistent disparities in access to resources and the ability to speak out (Down to Earth, 2014).

Gender equality is considered a critical element in achieving decent work for all women and men, in order to effect social and institutional change that leads to sustainable development with equity and growth. Gender equality refers to equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities that all persons should enjoy, regardless of whether one is born male or female. In the Philippines, Lazaro (2000) reported that being married make farmers work harder, more receptive to innovations, hence, more productive. However, Elias (2013) stated that civil status has no bearing to technology receptiveness and adoption also not directly significantly correlated to participation.

Given that women are usually in a disadvantaged position in the workplace compared to men, promotion of gender equality implies explicit attention to women's needs and perspectives. At the same time, there are also significant negative effects of unequal power relations and expectations on men and boys due to stereotyping about what it means to be a male. Instead, both women and men, and boys and girls, should be free to develop their abilities and make choices – without limitations set by rigid gender roles and prejudices – based on personal interests and capacities.

International Labor Organization (2004) has adopted an integrated approach to gender equality and decent work. This means working to enhance equal employment opportunities through measures that also aim to improve women's access to education, skills training and healthcare – while taking women's role in the care economy adequately into account. Examples of these include implementing measures to help workers balance work and family responsibilities, and providing workplace incentives for the provision of childcare and parental leave.

The concept of bringing gender issues into the mainstream of society was clearly established as a global strategy for promoting gender equality in the Platform for Action adopted at the United Nations Fourth World Conference on Women, held in Beijing

(China) in 1995. It highlighted the necessity to ensure that gender equality is a primary goal in all area(s) of social and economic development (Council of Europe, 2020).

Furthermore, mainstreaming a gender perspective is the process of assessing the implications for women and men of any planned action, including legislation, policies or programs, in any area and at all levels. It is a strategy for making the concerns and experiences of women as well as of men an integral part of the design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of policies and programs in all political, economic and societal spheres, so that women and men benefit equally, and inequality is not perpetuated. The ultimate goal of mainstreaming is to achieve gender equality.

The twin challenges of building pathways to sustainable development and achieving gender equality have never been more pressing. As the world moves towards the post-2015 development agenda, the present World Survey not only shows why each challenge is so important, but also who both challenges must be addressed together in ways that fully realize the human rights of women and girls and help countries to make the transition to sustainable development. The centrality of gender equality, women's empowerment and the realization of women's rights in achieving sustainable development has been increasingly recognized in recent decades. This recognition is evident in a number of international norms and agreements, including principle 20 of the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development, adopted in 1992, in its statement regarding the full participation of women being essential to achieving sustainable development (Council of Europe, 2020).

In the context of the world of work, equality between women and men includes the following elements: equality of opportunity and treatment in employment, equal remuneration for work of equal value, equal access to safe and healthy working environments and to social security, equality in association and collective bargaining, equality in obtaining meaningful career development, balance between work and home life that is fair to both women and men, and equal participation in decision-making at all levels (International Labor Organization, 2004).

GAD focuses on the principle that development is for all; male or female and that they should enjoy equal rights and opportunities to achieve a full and meaningful satisfying life. It recognizes the legitimacy of gender equality as fundamental value that should be reflected in development. It is also a means for achieving development. It contends that women are active agenda of development and not just passive recipient of development assistance (Natan, 2018).

GAD focus primarily on two major frameworks, Gender Roles and Social Relations Analysis. Gender role focus on social construction of identities within the household, it also reveals the expectations from 'maleness and femaleness' in their relative access to resources. Social relations analysis exposes the social dimensions of hierarchical power relations imbedded in social institutions; also it's determining influence on 'the relative position of men and women in society. In an attempt to create gender equality, (denoting

women having same opportunities as men, including ability to participate in the public sphere) GAD policies aim to redefine traditional gender role expectations (De Guzman, 2020). The Philippine Plan for Gender and Development, 1995-2025, is a National Plan that addresses, provides and pursues full equality and development for men and women. Approved and adopted by former President Fidel V. Ramos as Executive No. 273, on September 8, 1995, it is the successor of the Philippine Development Plan for Women, 1989-1992 adopted by Executive No. 348 of February 17, 1989.

Three years after, DENR Administrative Order No. 98 – 15 dated May 27, 1998 came up as the Revised Guidelines on the Implementation of Gender and Development (GAD) Activities in the Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) in order to strengthen the DENR GAD Focal Point System and accomplishing the GAD vision “Partnership of Empowered Men and Women for Sustainable Development”.

Republic Act No. 9710, otherwise known as the Magna Carta of Women was approved on August 14, 2009 which mandates non-discriminatory and pro-gender equality and equity measures to enable women’s participation in the formulation, implementation and evaluation of policies and plan for national, regional and local development (PITAH, 2019). A Memorandum Circular No. 2011 – 01 dated October 21, 2011 was released addressing to all Government Departments including their attached agencies, offices, bureaus, State Universities and Colleges (SUCs), Government-Owned and Controlled Corporations (GOCCs) and all other government instrumentalities as their guidelines and procedures for the establishment, strengthening and institutionalization of the GAD Focal Point System (GFPS).

Moreover, meaningful participation requires that individuals are entitled to participate in the decisions that directly affect them, including in the design, implementation, and monitoring of health interventions. In practice, meaningful participation may take on a number of different forms, including informing people with balanced, objective information, consulting the community to gain feedback from the affected population, involving or working directly with communities, collaborating by partnering with affected communities in each aspect of decision making including the development of alternatives and identification of solutions, and empowering communities to retain ultimate control over the key decisions that affect their wellbeing.

Gender equality has a strong anxiety to the world and their interest was to address differences between man and women in terms of needs and responsibilities. In their effort to achieve this in Nigeria, government established Women in Agricultural extension (WIA) programme by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and World Bank and put it under Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) so that they will help women in accessing the agricultural information, resources and reduce gender discrepancy level . This approach also called Women in Agriculture (WIA). With this, Agricultural Development Programme is facing serious challenges of gender inequality and their main problem is poor understanding of what gender means. Gender is a principal organiser and controller

of activities between people in Agricultural production, reproduction, distribution and consumption. It also means roles and responsibilities and it depends on the cultural belief of the society giving to man and woman. Inability to understand gender may result to gender blindness and increases gender differences. Good understanding of gender will help programme planners and policy makers in agricultural development to achieve their objectives. Gender did not mean men or women rather how they associate. Gender is a social practice, idea and attributes giving to male or female (Chekene, 2018).

The contribution of women to agricultural development will not be overemphasized. Women provide 60-80% of food and more than half of the global foods are supply by the women. Women spend 85-90% of labour force on household food processing and preparation. Time allocation study found that women labour is highly significant than man. Moreover, girls do more work in household than boys. Again 60- 90% of total farm work is done by women. These covered wide range of activities such as land clearing, tilling, weeding, planting, and application of fertilizer, harvesting, threshing, winnowing, milling, transporting and marketing among others. Despite these facts, agricultural and economic policies give less priority to female. In Africa if gender equality been adopted properly it may result to (20%- 30%) increase in yield output and 2.5-4.0% increase in global yield and this will alleviate global hunger by 12-17% (Doss, 2011).

The Gender And Development (GAD) give emphasis on both men and women and how they interact to one another. This will reduce gender inequality, promote gender equality, power relation and brings solution to developmental problems. This GAD approach considered gender at the center focal point of development and its gender related approach. This approach addresses women that experience restrictions in accessing resources, empowerment and participation through equal treatment given to all. Gender And Development consider both men and women address inequalities that prevent development, and this commitment will be sustainable for future. Holistic approach of GAD has impact on developmental agenda in many sectors. Therefore, agricultural production system may find it difficult to separate women from men (Kashim 2018).

To enhance the efficacy and responsiveness of diverse projects and programs aimed at advancing the sustainable management of resources within agroforests, forests, and watersheds, thereby contributing to environmental quality and the betterment of residents' lives, with a particular emphasis on fostering gender inclusion, this research endeavor is initiated.

Framework of the Study

The study is guided by the principle and concept of gender participation on the roles of men and women. The framework of the study employs the input-process-output model (Figure 1). The input variables are the socio- demographic profile of the respondents, gender participation of the respondents in project management, site preparation, and maintenance and protection activities within upland agroforests, gender participation on

the adopted soil and water conservation practices, support/assistance provided by the government and other agencies and problems encountered by the respondents.

The process involved the formulation of a questionnaire, pre-testing and floating of questionnaires combined with direct interview and observation method, survey and presentation of data gathered and the analysis of data. The outputs are the status of gender participation in the sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests.

Fig 1. Framework of the Study

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to determine the gender participation in the sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests.

Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What are the socio-demographic profile of respondents in barangay Arosip, Bacnotan, barangay Lacong, San Gabriel and barangay Casilagan in Naguilian, La Union, Philippines?
2. What is the extent of gender participation of the respondents in project management, site preparation, and maintenance and protection activities within upland agroforests?
3. What is the extent of gender participation in the adopted soil and water conservation practices?
4. What are the support/assistance provided by the government and other agencies?
5. What is the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by the respondents with regards to sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests?

Definition of Terms

Agroforestry is the growing of trees and association of crops or animals by the respondents.

Alley cropping refers to the cultivation of food, forage or specialty crops between rows of trees that is adopted by the respondents.

Conservation refers to the wise utilization of soil, water and natural resources found in the area.

Development refers to the significant positive change within the area.

Diversion canal refers to the soil and water conservation practice of the respondents to divert surface run offs to other bodies of water.

Gender participation refers to the involvement of male and female respondents in the management and development of the CAFF Upland Development Extension Project.

Intercropping refers to one of the soil and water conservation practices of the respondents which involve growing two or more crops in the same unit of land.

Mulching refers to the soil and water conservation practice adopted by the respondents which is application of some materials to the surface of the soil to retain soil moisture.

Multiple cropping refers to the various crops cultivated in a given unit of land.

Participatory approach refers to the involvement of people in the community in project planning, implementation and decision making.

Pre-test is a survey conducted in collecting data from the respondents before the final survey to further improve the contents of the questionnaire.

Reforestation refers to tree planting, replanting and regeneration activities in the barangay.

Respondents refer to the recipients/beneficiaries of the upland development extension projects of the College of Agroforestry and Forestry in barangay Arosip, Bacnotan, barangay Lacong, San Gabriel and barangay Casilagan, La Union who were interviewed and were responsible in supplying the necessary information asked in the questionnaire.

Socio-demographic profile refers to the characteristics of the respondents which include age, gender, education, income and location/study sites.

Soil and Water Conservation (SWC) practices are the practices such as intercropping, multiple cropping, terracing, mulching, alley cropping, water harvesting and other activities adopted by respondents in their farms.

Sustainable management is a handling of resources that meets the needs of the present generation while sustaining the needs of the future generation.

Uplands are the areas where the respondents reside and make a living.

Terracing refers to the soil conservation practice applied to prevent rainfall runoff on sloping land from accumulating and causing serious erosion which was adopted by the respondents.

Water harvesting refers to the collection of runoff for productive use that is adopted by the respondents.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive statistics was used in the study. It described the natural situation as it exist at the time of the study and explore the case of the particular phenomena with the use of a prepared questionnaire with direct interview and observation methods to the different respondents.

Sources of Data

There were 145 respondents composed of families and barangay officials coming from barangays Arosip, Casilagan, and Lacong within the municipalities of Bacnotan, Naguilian and San Gabriel, La Union (Table 1).

The study was conducted from February to May 2020. The locale of the study is presented in Figure 2.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents by Location

Location/Barangay	Male (n)	Percentage (%)	Female (n)	Percentage (%)
1. Arosip, Bacnotan, La Union	32	34.04	18	35.29
2. Casilagan, Naguilian, La Union	44	46.80	26	50.98
3. Lacong, San Gabriel, La Union	18	19.14	7	13.73
Total:	94	100.00	51	100.00

Fig 2. Locale of the Study

Instrumentation and Data Collection

Communications (Appendix A) were sent to the barangay officials prior to the conduct of the survey. Coordination was properly observed. Letters were addressed to the head officials requesting permission to gather the needed data from the respondents of the study (Plates 1 & 2).

Plate 1. Coordination of the Researcher with the Barangay. Captain Ferlyn Santiago of Arosip, Bacnotan, La Union

Plate 2. Coordination of the Researcher with the Barangay Captain Dominador Lilan of Lacong, San Gabriel, La Union

Questionnaires (Appendix B) were prepared, pre-tested and finalized prior to the distribution/administration of the improved questionnaires to the respondents. Floating of questionnaires coupled with direct interview and observation was done during the actual visit to the area. Barangay officials, community leaders, elders and other selected members of the community were interviewed. The purpose of the interview is to validate the data from the socio-demographic profile of respondents particularly on their customs, traditions, and other practices on forest resource utilization and upland agriculture.

Focus group discussion was conducted during an assembly of the three upland barangays to further confirm other information and data to determine their awareness, insights and expectations regarding sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests. Sample photos on the gathering of data from the barangays are presented in Plates 3 and 4.

Plate 3. Conduct of Interview in Barangay Casilagan, Naguilian, La Union

Plate 4. The Researcher Interviewing Two Respondents in Barangay Lacong, San Gabriel, La Union

The data collected were as follows: 1. socio-demographic profile of respondents; 2. gender participation on the different activities of regarding sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests 3. gender participation on the adopted Soil and Water Conservation (SWC) practices; 5. support/assistance provided by the government and other agencies and; 6. problems encountered by the recipients of the projects.

Analysis of Data

The data collected were tabulated, presented, and analyzed using the descriptive statistical tools such as frequency counts, percentages and means.

On the gender participation of the respondents in project management, site preparation, and maintenance and protection activities within upland agroforests and adopted soil and water conservation practices, the descriptive quantitative and range of values were used in the interpretation of data shown below.

Numerical Values	Range Values	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20 - 5.00	Very Highly Participated
4	3.40 - 4.19	Highly Participated
3	2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Participated
2	1.80 - 2.59	Fairly Participated
1	1.00 - 1.79	Not Participated

The data on the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by the were interpreted following the numerical values, range of values and descriptive rating shown below.

Numerical Values	Range Values	Descriptive Rating
5	4.20 - 5.00	Very Highly Serious
4	3.40 - 4.19	Highly Serious
3	2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Serious
2	1.80 - 2.59	Fairly Serious
1	1.00 - 1.79	Not Serious

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-demographic Profile

Table 2 shows the socio-demographic profile of respondents in terms of age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, tenure of land, land area cultivated, monthly income, occupation aside from farming and distance of their houses to the farms.

Gender

A great majority (94 or 64.83%) of the respondents are male while many of the female respondents are 51 or 35.17%. This implies that upland farming is dominated by men.

Age

The table presents that many (48 or 33.10%) of the respondents belonged to the age bracket of 41-50 years, 36 or 24.83% belonged to 51-60, 29 or 20% are 61 years and above, few (19 or 13.10%) are ages 21-30 years and 13 or 8.97% belonged to the age bracket of 31-40 years old. This confirmed the report from the data of the Philippine Institute for Development studies as shown on Figure 3 that majority (61.50%) of the workers in the agriculture field belong to the age bracket 25-54 in 2015 as well in 2008. It further explains that since 2008, the age profile of agricultural workers has increased slightly, i.e. higher proportion of older workers, and a smaller proportion of youngest workers. This is consistent with long term trends in farming: the average age of 46 to 56 years in 1966. Aging of farmers is common to developing countries, where younger workers tend to opt for nonfarm occupations (Cabiladas, 2019).

Civil Status

A great majority (104 or 71.72%) of respondents are married, few (29 or 20%) are single and 12 or 8.28% are widowed. This implies that the respondents are generally of the middle age and are still capable of farming activities for quite a number of years. According to the findings of Elias (2013), civil status has no bearing to technology receptiveness and adoption and also not directly significantly correlated to participation.

Table 2. Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents

Profile	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	94	64.83
Female	51	35.17
Total	145	100.00
Age		
21-30	19	13.10
31-40	13	8.97
41-50	48	33.10
51-60	36	24.83
61 years & above	29	20.00
Total	145	100.00
Civil Status		
Single	29	20.00
Married	104	71.72
Widower	12	8.28
Total	145	100.00
Educational Attainment		
Elementary	56	36.62
High School	53	36.55
Vocational	22	15.17
College	14	9.66
Total	145	100.00
Tenure of Land		
Owner Operator	57	39.31
Leaseholder/Tenant	88	60.69
Total	145	100.00
Number of Years in Farming		
5 years and below	27	18.62
6-8 years	37	25.52
9 years & above	81	55.86
Total	145	100.00
Land Area Cultivation		
Below 1 ha.	60	41.38
1-5 has.	67	46.21
11 has. & above	18	12.41
Total	145	100.00

Continuation of Table 2

Profile	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Monthly Income		
3, 000 & below	27	18.62
3,001 – 5,000	56	38.62
5,001 – 7,000	28	19.31
7,001 – 9,000	20	13.79
9,001 & above	14	9.66
Total	145	100.00
Occupation Aside From Farming		
Gov't worker/official	21	14.48
Laborer	59	40.69
Store owner/ buy & sell	33	22.76
Caretaker	8	5.52
Carpentry	9	6.21
Jeepney Driver	7	4.83
OFW	8	5.52
Total	145	100.00
Distance of the Households to the Farms		
500 m & below	44	30.34
501 m to 1km	57	39.31
1.1 km to 2km	30	20.69
2.1 km & above	14	9.66
Total	145	100.00

Source: Philippine Institute for Development Studies (Briones, 2017)

Fig. 3. Distribution of Workers by Age Bracket in Agriculture Sector, 2015 and 2008 (%)

Educational Attainment

Many of the respondents are elementary (56 or 36.62%) and high school (53 or 36.55%) graduates, few of them have vocational course (22 or 15.17%) and 14 or 9.66% are college graduates. This scenario is common in upland areas. Their incapability to access higher level of education is constrained due to poverty which was mentioned during the interview. Poverty is a multifaceted problem that includes factors such as finances, food supply, health, housing, sanitation, politics, infrastructure, war, and education (Walingo,2006).

Studies showed that poverty levels are strongly linked to educational attainment. Two-thirds of poor households are headed by people with only an elementary school education or below. Access to quality education is identified as a key pathway out of poverty. Low national levels of education are detrimental to development under any circumstances; but in the fast developing, technologically globalized world the need for adult education and lifelong learning strategies for all populations is particularly urgent. Without such education, each household's ability to resist societal challenges and shocks is compromised, and human capital decreases. The recognition of the need to improve household food security and women's economic empowerment follows upon the realization of the great role they play as gatekeepers to national development and nutrition. This situation has led to the implementation of agricultural projects that target women smallholder farmers, projects that constitute one of the major strategies to expand agricultural output in rural areas (Dixon, 2017).

In Brazil, education is considered the correct way towards promoting equal conditions between men and women. In their schools, policies were aimed at encouraging non-discriminatory practices, respect for diversity and sexual orientation, as well as encouraging the interests of girls in non-traditional disciplines (Child Fund International, 2019).

The importance of education in developing countries cannot be overstated. Education can be the catalyst needed to pull families and communities out of the cycle of poverty. Knowledge gives children the power to dream of a better future and the confidence needed to pursue a full education, which in turn will help generations to come. Education also makes a significant difference for adults, particularly when it applies to day-to-day life, including nutrition, healthcare and gender equity. When adults learn, they become role models to their children, who also wish to learn. Moreover, education improves gender equity and breaks the cycle of poverty (Child Fund International, 2019).

Tenure of Land

Results showed that a great majority of the respondents (88 or 60.69%) are leaseholders or tenants while the remaining 57 or 39.31% are owner operators. The upland areas are the place where increasing population of the “poorest of the poor” lives and where most of its population do not own the land they till ending them up as leaseholders or tenants. This condition conforms with the study of Cruz et al. (1986), that the sloping uplands occupy about 55 percent of the with an estimated upland inhabitants of 17.8 million who are primarily poor farming families with insecure land tenure (United Nation Development Program, 2009).

Monthly Income

Many (56 or 38.62%) of the respondents earn a monthly income of Php. 3,001 to Php. 5,000, 28 or 19.31% earn Php. 5,001 to Php. 7,000, 27 or 18.62% earn below Php. 3,000, and few (14 or 9.66%) earn an income of Php. 9, 0001 and above. This indicates that their low income could hardly sustain the basic needs of their families. This situation is attributed with the small farm size they are cultivating, thus limiting agricultural production.

Occupation aside from Farming

Many (59 or 40.69%) of the respondents are laborers, 33 or 22.76% are store owners or engaged in buying and selling of goods, 21 or 14.48% are government workers or officials, 9 or 6.21% are carpenters, few (8 or 5.52"%) are caretakers and OFW's, and 7 or 4.83% are jeepney drivers. As residents of upland areas, “hand to mouth subsistence” is prevalent where farming is the primary source to earn a living but they opted to engage in other jobs/occupations for additional income to provide the needs of their families.

Distance of Household to Farms

Many of the respondents (57 or 39.31%) lived within 501 meters to 1 kilometer from their farms. The rest lived (44 or 30.34%) 500 meters to 1 kilometer, (30 or 20.69%) lived 1.1 to 2 kilometers, and 14 or 9.66% lived 2.1 kilometers and above which is closer to the farms they till.

The uplands are characterized as rolling to steep areas where both agriculture and forestry are practiced on slopes ranging upward from 18 percent. Distance of household to the farm is also a common feature in the upland communities. Nevertheless, distances of their households to the farms is a slight problem because the residents are used to walking far distances in the inaccessibility of good roads from farm to households as well as market where they bring to sell their agricultural products.

Gender Participation in Various Project Management, Site Preparation, and Maintenance and Protection Activities Within Upland Agroforests

Project management is the practice of leading the work of a team to achieve goals and meet success at a specified time. To achieve all of the set goals is the primary challenge of project management. It is the application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques applied to project activities in order to meet the project requirements. Project management is a process that includes planning, putting the project plan into action, and measuring progress and performance.

Members/beneficiaries (men and women) of the project can participate in a variety of ways, and to different levels of influence, in identifying needs, generating solutions, planning new initiatives and service delivery to ensure an effective implementation of the different activities under the program management.

Table 3 presents gender participation on the different activities of sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests. There are two categories of activities considered namely: (a) project management that includes attendance to meetings, discussion, financial management and planning/decision making; and (b) site preparation, maintenance and protection activities such as weeding/clearing, hole digging, planting, watering, fertilizing and replanting.

Table 3. Gender Participation in the Project Management, Site Preparation and Maintenance and Protection Activities Within Upland Agroforests

Activities	Men		Women	
	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating
A. Project Management				
• Attendance to meetings	4.43	Very Highly Participated	3.84	Highly Participated
• Discussions	4.09	Highly Participated	3.26	Moderately Participated
• Financial management	3.31	Moderately Participated	4.10	Very Highly Participated
• Planning/decision making	3.20	Highly Participated	2.75	Moderately Participated
B. Site Preparation, Maintenance and Protection				
• Weeding/Clearing	3.70	Highly Participated	3.00	Moderately Participated
• Hole Digging	3.54	Highly Participated	2.59	Fairly Participated
• Planting	4.21	Very Highly Participated	3.68	Highly Participated

• Watering	3.70	Highly Participated	3.09	Moderately Participated
• Fertilizing	2.97	Moderately Participated	2.16	Fairly Participated
• Replanting	4.06	Very Highly Participated	3.24	Moderately Participated

Findings revealed that the male respondents registered very highly in their attendance (4.43) as against their female counter part with a rating of 3.84 which is highly participated. From the interview, women claimed that their attendance to meetings was due to their household chores and have to attend to the needs of their children. Instead, their husbands take the responsibility in attending the meetings called for by their officials.

As to the discussions on the management of the project, men rated highly participated (4.09) while women are moderately participated (3.26). This holds true to the report of Edwards (2020) that women were afraid to speak up during meetings for they thought that they did not have good ideas, do not want to speak too loud or aggressive, do not think on their feet, or were afraid of being wrong. She added that a woman speaks up in the workplace, she walks a thin tightrope: asserting her views without coming across as too loud or aggressive. As a result, many women opt to stay silent rather than risk saying something wrong (Edwards, 2017). She also reported men do a whopping 75% of the talking during the average business meeting. Preliminary results from Partners In Leadership research confirmed this finding that women above men still struggle to find their voice in the room.

In financial management, men have moderate participation (3.31) and the women have very highly participation (4.1). During the 2015 World Bank Financial Capability Survey, it was reported that women have higher financial literacy than men (World Bank, 2010).

Projects are the basic building blocks of development. Without successful project identification, preparation and implementation, development plans are no more than wishes and developing nations would remain stagnant or regress. Projects, Adams (2019) claims, projects are the “cutting edge” of development. Hirschman calls them “privileged particles of the development process. Programs and projects are increasingly used in developing countries in the process of economic and social development,” the United Nations proclaims. “They represent a crucial element in both the formulation and implementation of development plans. Most of the administrators are more directly concerned with program and project administration than with other, more generic aspects of public administration.” For nearly a quarter of a century, projects have also been the primary instruments for grant, credit, loan and technical aid to developing countries by international assistance agencies.

Within the home, as outside it, power and authority tend to rest on men, but the women have their own areas of authority. Women decide on how their children will be raised and

educated, how earnings will be allocated, when and how much of their crop harvest will be sold, and what to feed their families. In contrast, men have greater say in such matters as investment, loans, and even the choice of contraceptive method (Shibata et al, 2020). But in some lowland Christian communities, women claim that even investments and loans are decided jointly by them and their spouses. Among rural households, however, women's decision-making power is almost nonexistent as there is very little chance for the children to stay in school, or very little earnings to be budgeted. Among some cultural groups in the Philippines, not even the children or the budget are considered as women's domain. Indeed, for women of these groups, there are too few opportunities for sharing power and too little decisions to be made. Information from group interviews conducted by the author in March 1994 suggests that part of the problem is women's ignorance about their legal rights, a concern overshadowed by the day-to-day anxieties of basic survival (Watson et al., 1999).

The participation of the male respondents obtained highly participation during planning sessions (3.20) while their female counterpart registered moderate participation (2.75).

It was mentioned by Davies et al. (2002) that in order for the planning profession to properly understand and accommodate women, planning professionals must consider women's uses and experiences of public space to be legitimate and important. He further stated that professional urban planners and designers and local government officials should not only seek women's active participation and input in planning processes, but they should also ensure that this participation and input is valued and used. Sometimes, women and girls do not communicate in the same way that professionals and decision-makers do. Women and girls might talk about their emotions and reactions instead of just plain facts. This can be difficult for professionals and decision-makers to understand at first. However, this does not mean that women's and girls' use and experiences of public space are not legitimate and important.

On site preparation, maintenance and protection, men rated very highly participated on planting (4.21) and replanting (4.06), highly participated on weeding (3.70), hole digging (3.54) and watering (3.70) while women rated high participation (3.68) on planting and other activities were rated moderate and fair participation. This result is medicating that men are doing more hard work in the farm compared to women.

Gender Participation in the Adopted Soil and Water Conservation Practices

Table 4 shows the Soil and Water Conservation practices adopted by the respondents. Male respondents have very high participation on agroforestry (5.0), alley

Table 4. Gender Participation in the Adopted Soil and Water Conservation (SWC) Practices

SWC Practices	Men		Women	
	Numeric Rating	Descriptive Rating	Numeric Rating	Descriptive Rating
1. Agroforestry (Agrisilvicultural Silvipastoral Agrisilvipastoral Intercropping)	5.0	Very Highly Adopted	4.61	Very Highly Participated
2. Alley cropping	3.46	Very Highly Adopted	3.04	Very Highly Participated
3. Multiple cropping	4.29	Very Highly Adopted	4.45	Very Highly Participated
4. Terracing	4.57	Very Highly Adopted	3.55	Highly Participated
5. Reforestation/afforestation	4.76	Very Highly Adopted	4.92	Very Highly Participated
6. Establishment of water harvester	4.67	Very Highly Adopted	3.49	Highly Participated
7. Diversion Canal	4.77	Very Highly Adopted	3.78	Highly Participated
8. Mulching	2.39	Fairly Adopted	2.24	Fairly Participated

cropping (3.46), multiple cropping (4.29), terracing (4.57), establishment of water harvester (4.67), reforestation and afforestation (4.76), establishment of diversion canals (4.77), while mulching is fairly adopted (2.39) by men. On the other hand, women have rated very highly participation to agroforestry (4.61), alley cropping (3.04), multiple cropping (4.45) and reforestation/afforestation (4.92).

Plate 5. Agroforestry System (integration of trees, crops animal) in Arosip, Bacnotan, La Union

Intercropping (Tiger Grasses with Papaya, Banana & Mahogany Trees)

Intercropping- Coconut, Mahogany & Gmellina

Goat and Carabao

Plate 6. Soil and Water Conservation Practices in Barangay Lacong, San Gabriel, La Union

Plate 7. Multiple Cropping in Barangay Casilagan, Naguilian, La Union

Plate 8. Multiple cropping (Cacao-Guyabano-Coffee-Papaya and Banana) in Lacong, San Gabriel, La Union

Both male and female respondents recorded fairly participation in mulching. The very highly participation of the respondents in the adopted soil and water conservation practices is due to the rolling and steeply features of the watershed location in the community especially in Casilagan, Naguilian and Lacong, San Gabriel, La Union. Hence, the residents especially the barangay officials in Casilagan, Naguilian, La Union were very conscious in protecting their forest areas because of its vulnerability to landslide and erosion. The seedlings planted and grown in barangay Casilagan, Naguilian, La Union were provided by DMMMSU-NLUC, Bacnotan, La Union (Plate 9).

Plate 9. Seedlings Planted during the Reforestation Activity within the Watershed Area in Barangay Casilagan, Naguilian, La Union

Farming as an occupation is dominated by males. However, Abeka, et al (2008) have shown that women were the ones who have led their households and communities in the development of agriculture coping strategies including food preservation, mixed cropping, water harvesting and irrigation, growing reliance on wild fruits and forest products.

In the study for coping strategies and perceptions of farmers on the roles of trees in climate change mitigation and adaptation in the upland barangays of Bacnotan, La Union, Fontanilla (2016), found out that fruit and forest trees with other crops, vegetable and livestock are already practiced by farmers and adopted integrated farming and agroforestry. Upland farmers in Bacnotan, La Union had adopted coping strategies such as diversified farming/cropping, planting of drought resistant crops, soil and water conservation methods, improved post-harvest technology, mulching, and improved irrigation system.

Onyekale and Madukwe (2010) explored the adaptation measures by crop farmers in the Southeast rainforest zone of Nigeria to climate change and revealed that portfolio diversification was the most used method as reported by 20% farmers. This strategy involves the use of improved crop varieties, intercropping and using different crop varieties that survive in adverse conditions. Other strategies used by farmers include the use of soil and conservation technologies (15%), changing planting dates (11.7%) and planting of trees. Makondo (2018) gave some indigenous adaptation strategies to climate variability by farmers, such include; fall back on previous harvest, rain water harvesting, diversification of livelihood and use of forecasts to prevent responding false start of rains.

Support/ Assistance Provided by the Government and other Agencies

The overall purpose of development assistance is to improve the livelihoods of citizens in recipient countries, especially the impoverished. Poverty reduction is internationally recognized as an important assistance issue component for poverty reduction. Support services come in many forms which are necessary in facilitating the process of agricultural development (DA, 1989). The effective delivery of basic social services and poverty-related programs at the local level will improve poverty reduction programs.

The support/assistance provided by the partners and other agencies is presented in Table 5. DMMMSU- NLUC, specifically the College of Agroforestry and Forestry provided technical assistance for upland farming and training on nursery management and plantation establishment at barangay Arosip, Bacnotan, La Union. On the other hand, DMMMSU-NLUC also provided seedlings to barangay Casilagan, Naguilian which were planted within the watershed area. Barangay Lacong was also provided with technical assistance in the adoption of soil and water conservation practices. San Gabriel, La Union is also a recipient of the La Union Agroforestry Upland Development Project (LUAUDP). Agroforestry technology and various soil and water conservation practices were being introduced to them which are still sustainable and being practiced by the residents up to these days because of its benefits and advantages it provided them.

Table 5. Support/ Assistance Provided by the Government and other Agencies

Support Providers	Support/Assistance Provided
A. DMMMSU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Planting Materials b. Financial Assistance c. Trainings/Seminars d. Technical Assistance e. IEC Materials
B. Other Partners	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Planting Materials b. Fertilizer c. Trainings/Seminars d. Technical Assistance e. Machineries
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DENR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> f. Planting Materials g. Trainings/Seminars h. Technical Assistance
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOST 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Machineries j. Trainings/Seminars k. Technical Assistance
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LGU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> l. Fund/ Financial assistance
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lorma College 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> m. Planting Materials

Aside from DMMMSU-NLUC, there are other assistance given to the recipients of the projects. Planting materials such as cacao seedlings were given by Lorma College to barangay Arosip, Bacnotan. Fertilizers were also given to them by the Department of Agriculture and trainings provided by DA and DOST.

Casilagan, Naguilian, La Union was observed to have an advantage for a continuous support from Department of Environment and Natural Resources. DENR is an agency concern in the protection of natural resources especially on women and indigenous peoples living in highly fragile and vulnerable ecosystems, coastal fishers and other poor smallholders and landless people. Since barangay Casilagan is located in a steepy area, DENR continued their financial and technical assistance in order to help the residents to sustainably manage and protect their watershed areas.

The Department of Science and Technology also continuously assisted residents in barangay Lacong, San Gabriel by providing them machineries of which included an egg sorter which was eventually entrusted to their cooperative.

Problems Encountered by the Respondents

This study is not only limited in collecting information on gender participation in the various activities with regards to sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests but likewise has end purpose of gathering information on the potential problems encountered by the recipients (both men and women) to be appropriately addressed.

Table 6 presents the degree of seriousness of the problems encountered by the respondents. Results showed that irregular commitment and insufficient knowledge about the sustainable management of resources were considered fairly serious by both men and women respondents while inadequate support was not serious for the men and fairly serious for the women. On the gender participation in discussion and planning session, women rated it as fairly serious while not serious for the men.

The trending and most controversial global issue and concern of today by government, non-government intuitions, administrators, program implementers, and development practitioners is gender. Since Boserup's assertion that development affects both men and women differently. His effort had served as an "eye opener" that gathered the interest among scholars, and policy makers. From then, various approaches were designed to address this issue. Some of which include Women in Development (WID) that shifted into Women and Development (WAD) and finally Gender And Development (GAD), all of which focus on the gender issues.

Table 6. Degree of Seriousness of Problems Encountered by the Respondents

Problems	Men		Women	
	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating
A. Farmers Problem				
1. Irregular Commitment of members	1.96	Fairly Serious	1.89	Fairly Serious
2. Insufficient knowledge about the project	2.35	Fairly Serious	2.17	Fairly Serious
B. Partner/Service Providers				
1. Irregular monitoring and evaluation of the project	1.99	Fairly Serious	2.01	Fairly Serious

2. Inadequate support from partners	1.73	Not Serious	1.83	Fairly Serious
C. Gender Participation				
1. Participation of women in discussion and planning sessions	1.71	Not Serious	1.81	Fairly Serious

From the results of this study, it points out that the most or the highly serious problem rest on the insufficient knowledge of women regarding the nature of the project, although not fairly serious as observed by male respondents.

Gender issue particularly on the participation of women and men in the various development endeavors as well as their roles in the community appeared to be not serious or fairly serious which seems to indicate that both men and women engaged in the project do not consider gender participation as a potential problem. Regardless who does the job, whose roles/responsible, what and why do not affect their performance as manifested in their participation in the various project activities.

Irregular commitment of members maybe due to land ownership. Most of the respondents were only tenants or leaseholders to the land they are tilling so it could be a contributory factor to that problem. The respondents have insufficient knowledge about the program because the original partners of CAFF DMMMSU-NLUC projects before were already old, hence they have entrusted farm cultivation activities to their nearest keens or children. Despite of their children’s unawareness of the origin/provider of the technologies, it did not hinder their interest in sustaining the adoption practices.

Since the duration of the memorandum of agreement between DMMMSU-NLUC and barangay Lacong, San Gabriel and Casilagan, Naguilian, La Union had already terminated, the projects were not regularly visited/monitored.

The inadequate support from partners and participation of women in discussion, planning sessions were rated fairly serious by women but not serious to men. In Nigeria, women in agriculture approach considered women activities to increase their level of participation in decision making and natural resource management (Quisumbing et al., 2014).

The absence of a strong internal project monitoring system often cannot be effectively evaluated. Project monitoring and evaluation are very crucial elements of project management. It aims to determine the relevance and fulfillment of objectives, development efficiency, effectiveness, impact and sustainability. Monitoring is a regular process that systematically collects data on specified indicators to provide management

and the main stakeholders of an ongoing development intervention with indications of the extent of progress and achievement of objectives. Taken literally, this is a demanding. From then, project monitoring and evaluation are now a routine part of project appraisal. In the early 1980s, several international agricultural development agencies recognized the problems in formulating effective agricultural monitoring and evaluation (World Bank, 2010).

Summary

The study was conducted to determine the status of gender participation in the sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests in La Union, Philippines from February 25 to May 25, 2020 with the following specific objectives: 1) to determine the socio-demographic profile of respondents; 2) gender participation on the different activities of the sustainable management of resources within upland agroforests; 3) gender participation on the adopted soil and water conservation practices; 4) support/assistance provided by the government and other agencies; and 5) problems encountered by the respondents of the project.

The salient findings of the study were the following:

A great majority (94 or 64.83%) of the respondents were males while many (51 or 35.17%) were females. Many (48 or 33.10%) of the respondents belonged to the age bracket 41-50 years and a great majority (104 or 71.72%) were married.

Many of the respondents were elementary (56 or 36.62%) and high school (53 or 36.55%) graduates, few obtained vocational courses (22 or 15.17%), and 14 or 9.66% were college graduates.

A great majority of the project respondents (88 or 60.69%) were leaseholders or tenants while the remaining 57 or 39.31% were owner operators.

Majority of the respondents (81 or 56.86%) have 9 years and above farming experience. Almost half of the respondents (67 or 46.21%) have 1.5 hectares farm land area, many (60 or 41.38%) have one hectare and below and few (18 or 12.41%) have 11 hectares and above. Many (56 or 38.62%) of the respondents earn an income of Php. 3,001 to Php. 5,000 and few (14 or 9.66%) earn an income of Php. 9, 0001 and above.

As to the other jobs/occupation that the respondents are engaged many (59 or 40.69%) are laborers, 33 or 22.76% are store owners or engaged in buying and selling of goods, 21 or 14.48% are government workers or officials, 9 or 6.21% are carpenters, few (8 or 5.52%) are caretakers and OFW's and 7 or 4.83% are jeepney drivers.

On the distance of their households to their farms, many (57 or 39.31%) have 501 meters to 1 kilometer distance. Some (44 or 30.34%) have 500 meters to 1 kilometer, few (30 or 20.69%) have 1.1 to 2 kilometers, 14 or 9.66% have a distance of 2.1 kilometers and

above. The 2.1 kilometers and above distance recorded the least percentage since the areas were already situated in the upland.

On their attendance in meetings, men respondents have very highly participation (4.43) while female respondents have highly participation (3.84). During discussions, men have highly participation (4.09) while the women have moderate participation (3.26). In financial management, men have moderate participation (3.31) and the women recorded very highly participation (4.1).

Male respondents have very highly participation in planting (4.21) and replanting (4.06), highly participation in weeding/clearing (3.70), hole digging (3.54), and watering (3.7), while fertilizing activity is moderately participated by men (2.97). Meanwhile, female respondents have highly participation to planting (3.68), moderately participation in weeding/clearing (3.0), watering (3.09), and replanting (3.24). Hole digging (2.59) and fertilizing (2.16) activities were fairly participated by women.

Male respondents have very high participation on agroforestry practice (5.0), alley cropping (3.46), multiple cropping (4.29), terracing (4.57), establishment of water harvester (4.67), reforestation and afforestation (4.76) and establishment of diversion canals (4.77), mulching is fairly participated (2.39) by men. On the other hand, women respondents have very highly participation to agroforestry practice (4.61), alley cropping (3.04), multiple cropping (4.45) and reforestation/afforestation (4.92). Mulching is fairly participated.

Aside from DMMMSU-NLUC, other agencies that extended their assistance to the beneficiaries or recipients of the project include DA, DOST, Lorma Colleges, and LGU.

Problems encountered by the respondents (both men and women) in the implementation of the CAFF upland development extension projects were: irregular commitment of members and insufficient knowledge about the project are considered fairly serious. This irregular monitoring and evaluation of the project and inadequate support by the partners/service providers are considered fairly serious by both men and women. On the gender participation, insufficient perceptions on the roles of women in the community are not serious however, the participation of women in discussion and planning sessions are fairly serious.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study the following conclusions were deduced:

1. A great majority of the respondents are males and married. Many belong to ages 41-50 years old. In terms of educational attainment, many of the respondents are elementary and high school graduates. A great majority of the respondents are leaseholders and tenants, have 1-5 hectares farm lots and mostly with a monthly income of Php. 3,001-5,000.00. Many of the respondents have 501 meters to one kilometer distance from their

households to the farm. Distances of 2.1 kilometers and above have the least percentage since the areas were already in the upland, thus their farms are mostly situated within the vicinity of their homes.

2. Both men and women from the three study sites have moderate to very highly participation on the different activities of the project such as attendance to meetings, discussions, financial management and planning/decision making; and on site preparation, maintenance and protection activities such as weeding, hole digging, planting, watering, fertilizing and replanting.

3. There is very highly participation of both men and women on the adopted soil and water conservation such as agroforestry practice, alley cropping, multiple cropping, establishment of water harvester, reforestation/afforestation and establishment of diversion canals. Mulching was fairly adopted while construction of fire lines was not adopted.

4. Planting materials, technical, financial, trainings/seminars and IEC materials were the support assistance provided by DMMMSU and other partner agencies (DENR, DA, DOST, LGU and Lorma College).

5. The fairly serious problems encountered by both men and women respondents from the study sites in the implementation of CAFF, DMMMSU-NLUC upland development extension projects were irregular commitment of members, insufficient knowledge about the project. For the partners/service providers, irregular monitoring and evaluation of the project by the implementers and inadequate support were considered fairly serious. Participation of women in discussion and planning sessions was rated fairly serious for the women.

Recommendations

Given the above mentioned conclusions, the following are recommended:

1. There must be a harmonious coordination among the respondents and implementers to increase their awareness on the beneficiaries' problems and needs to be addressed;

2. Project implementers must clearly discuss the nature/overview of the projects, goals and objectives, the benefits they get from the projects as well as its advantages to the improvement, conservation, protection leading to a sustainable natural resources and watersheds;

3. Relevant trainings and seminars must be conducted to equip them on the appropriate management and protection of the established projects;

4. Regular monitoring and evaluation of the project activities must be observed to ensure its smooth operation that would consequently lead to the attainment of the project goals and objectives;

5. To institute an approach or strategy to encourage the active participation of both men and women in the community in all the activities in the designed project to be established.
6. To conduct a seminar focused on the following; gender participation/roles of men and women, and gender equality in all development endeavors (projects programs) and the like.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As the author of this research project, I affirm that the following ethical standards have been diligently observed throughout this study. Firstly, before their participation, all respondents were provided with comprehensive information regarding the purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits of the research, ensuring their informed consent. It was made explicitly clear that participants had the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point without consequence. Moreover, strict measures were implemented to maintain the anonymity of all respondents, ensuring their confidentiality and privacy were upheld throughout the research process. Furthermore, the well-being of respondents was of paramount importance, and steps were taken to safeguard their physical and psychological welfare. Any potential risks to participants were carefully assessed and mitigated to the best of our ability. Additionally, I declare that no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of this study. The research was carried out with integrity and objectivity, devoid of any bias or influence from personal, financial, or professional affiliations. Moreover, plagiarism in any form was strictly avoided, and all sources of information were appropriately cited and attributed following academic standards. Every effort was made to ensure the originality and authenticity of the research findings. Furthermore, the interpretation of the findings was conducted without bias, and rigorous analysis was undertaken to present an accurate representation of the results. Lastly, I confirm that the results of this study are intended solely for research purposes and will be utilized to contribute to the academic understanding of the subject matter. The findings will not be used for any other purpose beyond scholarly inquiry and advancement.

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Consult not your fears but your hopes and your dreams. Think not about your frustrations, but about your unfulfilled potential. Concern yourself not with what you tried and failed in, but with what it is still possible for you to do.- Pope John XXIII

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LMW

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APPENDIX
(The Research Instrument)

**GENDER PARTICIPATION IN THE SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF
RESOURCES WITHIN UPLAND AGROFORESTS IN LA UNION, PHILIPPINES**

Direction: Please answer the following items to the best of your knowledge by writing the information requested on the space provided for. Rest assured that your answer would be treated confidential.

I. Socio-demographic Profile of the Respondents

Name of respondents: _____

Address: _____

A. Age

___ 21-30

___ 31-40

___ 41-50

___ 51-60

___ 61 years and above

B. Gender

___ Male

___ Female

C. Civil Status:

___ Single

___ Married

___ Widower

D. Educational Attainment:

___ Elementary Graduate

___ High School Graduate

___ Vocational Graduate

___ College Graduate

___ Others

E. Tenure of Land

___ Owner Operator

___ Leaseholder/Tenant

F. Number of Year/s in Farming

___ 5 years and below

___ 6 years to 8 years

___ 9 years and above

G. Land Area Cultivation (in hectares)

___ below 1 ha.

- ___ 1-5 has.
- ___ 6-10has.
- ___ 11has. and above

H. Monthly income

- ___ P3,000 and below
- ___ P3,001-P5,000
- ___ P5,001-P7,000
- ___ P7,001-P9,000
- ___ P9,001 and above

I. Occupation aside from farming:

- | | |
|--------------------------------|-----------------|
| ___ Laborer | ___ Carpentry |
| ___ Painter | ___ Store owner |
| ___ Caretaker | ___ Housekeeper |
| ___ Government Worker/Official | ___ Driver |
| ___ Others, pls. Specify | |

J. Distance of the House to the Farm

- ___ 500 meters and below
- ___ 501 meters to 1 kilometer
- ___ 1.1 kilometer to 2 kilometers
- ___ 2.1 kilometers and above

II. Gender Participation in the Project Management, Site Preparation, and Maintenance and Protection Activities within Upland Agroforests

Direction: Please check (/) the appropriate number or letter that reflects the extent of your involvement in various activities. Be guided with the following scale:

**5- Very Highly Participated 4- Highly Participated 3- Moderately Participated
2- Fairly Participated 1- Not Participated**

A. Project Management Activities	Gender						
	5	4	3	2	1	Male	Female
A. Conduct of meetings							
B. Discussions							
C. Financial management							
D. Planning Sessions							

B. Site Preparation and Maintenance and Protection	Gender						
	5	4	3	2	1	Male	Female
A. Weeding/Clearing							
B. Hole Digging							
C. Planting							
D. Watering							
E. Fertilizing							
F. Replanting							

Part III. Gender Participation in the Adopted Soil and Water Conservation Practices

Soil and Water Conservation Practices	Gender						
	5	4	3	2	1	Male	Female
A. Agroforestry							
B. Alley cropping							
C. Mulching							
D. Multiple Cropping							
E. Terracing							
F. Reforestation/Afforestation							
G. Establishment of Water Harvester							
H. Establishment of Controls (checkdam, diversion canals etc.)							
I. Mulching							
J. Others (pls. specify)							

IV. Support/Assistance Provided to the Respondents by the Government and Other Agencies

Items Provided	Sponsoring Agencies
planting materials	
fertilizers	
machineries	
funding /financial assistance	
trainings /seminars	
Technical assistance	
others, please specify	

V. Problems encountered by the respondents

Direction: Please check them according to the seriousness of problems you have encountered.

5 Very Highly Serious; 4 Highly Serious 3 Moderately Serious;
2 Highly Serious; and 1 Not serious

Problems encountered	5	4	3	2	1	Male	Female
A. Farmers Problem							
Irregular commitment of members							
Insufficient knowledge about the program							
Others, please specify							
B. Partners/Service Providers	5	4	3	2	1	Male	Female
Irregular Monitoring and Evaluation of the project							
Inadequate support							
Others, please specify							
C. Gender Participation	5	4	3	2	1	Male	Female
Insufficient perception on the roles of women in the community							
Participation of women in discussion, planning sessions							
Others, please specify							